

Judicial Review and the Mandamus Remedy: Realizing the Promise of Article 21A

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Abstract

This research paper explores the policy achievement of government schemes like Sarv Shiksha Abhiyan, Mahyamik Shiksha Abhiyan, Teachers Training and Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan on government schools or government aided schools in the states & Union Territories through secondary data available on the websites of Ministry of Education, CAG, World Bank, UNICEF, Annual Status of Education Report facilitated by PRATHAM published articles and reputed newspapers. In this research paper, an effort is made to find out the scope of judicial review in Indian school education system of government schools and government aided schools under, article 14, 21-A of the constitution, the RTE Act, the 2009 and the RPwD Act, 2016. During this research different schemes sponsored by the central government in government schools & government aided schools of all states & Union Territories were analysed particularly in the context of those children coming from weaker sections, disadvantaged backgrounds and disabled categories. In this paper an attempt is made to find answer to following legal issues:

1. Whether the present state of school education in States & Union Territories violates international obligation, articles 14, 21 and 21-A of Indian Constitution?
2. What are the legal grounds available for judicial review by writ of mandamus in education system of government schools & government aided schools?

Keywords

Judicial review, Mandamus, Article 21-A, School education, right to free & compulsory education, Sarv Shiksha Abhiyan, Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan, Children with Special Need, Weaker Section, Disadvantaged Group, the RTE Act, quality education, USIDE+, PRATHAM, NAS, ASER, CAG Report.

Introduction

On 11 Dec 1992 India had ratified and accessed "the United Nation Convention on the Rights of the Child".[1] Almost after eight years of gap, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan[2] was launched in year 2001-02 with the aim to provide useful and relevant elementary education for all children falling in the age group 6 to 14 years by 2010 and also to bridge social, regional and gender gaps, with the active participation of the community in the management of schools. Its objectives were as under.[3]

1. To make all children complete five years of primary schooling by 2007.
2. To make all children complete eight years of elementary schooling by 2010.
3. To focus on elementary education of acceptable quality with emphasis on education for life.
4. To achieve universal retention of the student by 2010.

Whereas these objectives are yet to be achieved in year 2026.

Article 21A was inserted by the 86th Amendment Act, 2002 in the Indian Constitution makes free and compulsory education for all children aged 6 to 14 years a fundamental right & puts obligation on the State for its implementation.[4] Another flagship scheme of the Central Government "the Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan", was launched in March 2009 with the aim to improve the quality & access to secondary school education.[5] Main objective of this scheme was to achieve a gross enrolment ratio of 75% for classes IX-X within five years of launch date and universalize retention by 2020.[6]

The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act, 2009 came into effect on 01 April 2010[7]. and in year 2015, India adopted the United Nation Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG-4) with the aim to ensure inclusive and quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all[8]. This goal ensures that all girls and boys complete free primary & secondary schooling by 2030.[9] It also aims to provide equal access to affordable vocational training, to eliminate gender & wealth disparities, and achieving universal access to quality higher education.[10]

Objective of study

This research paper explores the policy achievement of government schemes like Sarv Shiksha Abhiyan, Mahyamik Shiksha Abhiyan, Teachers Training and Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan on government schools and government aided schools in the states & Union

Territories through secondary data available on the websites of Ministry of Education, CAG, World Bank, UNICEF, Annual Status of Education Report facilitated by PRATHAM and reputed newspapers with the aim to find out the grounds for judicial review in school education.

Review of Literature

This paper is based on the various reviews and cases which are discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

In continuum of SDG-4, Department of School Education & Literacy, Ministry of Education, Govt. of India has launched "Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan" an integrated scheme for school education covering the entire gamut from pre-school to class XII in year 2018-19.[11] It also includes the main features of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Rastriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan & Teacher's Education Programme too.[12] At last, National Education Policy (NEP)-2020 was notified in year 2020 which has superseded the NEP 1986.[13]

But all previous reports including latest data available on the official websites of Ministry of Education, CAG, NCERT, UNICEF, United Nation & PRATHAM (a reputed NGO) expose learning & PTR crisis exposing the noncompliance of the RTE Act, 2009, underachievement of objectives of Sarv Shiksha Abhiyan, Teacher's Training & Samagr Shiksha Abhiyan too.[14] The Comptroller and Auditor General of India Report on School Education in the State of Odisha covering the financial year 2018 to 2023, was signed & made public on Sept 2025 where the Auditors have made very serious observation on data accuracy on school infrastructure & facilities in the official records, lack of basic infrastructure, adverse Pupil Teachers ratio, adverse Student Classroom ratio, under utilisation of funds, negligence towards the care of Children with Special Needs, mismanagement in rationalisation of teacher's posting in the schools, lack of habitation wise mapping of schools and many other crucial issues impacting the performance of government administered and government aided schools of Odisha were highlighted in it, [15] similarly others states & Union Territories also lacks in school infrastructure, drinking water facility, library, Pupil Teacher Ratio, digital education, learning outcome of students, & other much needed facilities including proper planning & resource management.[16]

Despite the constitutional guarantee under the above-mentioned constitutional & statutory provisions, policy commitments under NEP-2020 and approval of total outlay of **Rs 294283.04 crore** for Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan for the period of 01/04/2021 to 31/03/2026[17] & proactive approach of the concerned ministry, official data reveals persistent deficiencies under following heads:[18]

- Weak implementation of NEP-2020 & RTE Act, 2009
- Poor School infrastructure and sanitation.
- Digital divide and inequitable access to school education across all states.
- Regional and inter-state disparity in Fund allocation by state government for school education.
- Transparency and accountability in school administration of government schools & government aided schools of States & Union Territories
- Errorful Data collection method pertaining to performance indicators & digitalisation of all such schools
- Teacher availability and Pupil Teacher Ratio.
- Infrastructure and accessibility.
- Learning outcomes
- Support services for children with disabilities & training of especially skilled teachers & staffs to support them
- Utilisation of allocated education funds
- Higher dropout rates in some States even at Primary level.
- Section 11 of the RTE Act, 2009 makes pre-primary education as state discretion not an enforceable right.

CAG Report on the schools of Odisha, reveals that the UDISE+ Report published by the Ministry of Education lacks accuracy[19] which is detrimental for the execution of policy objectives as it gives misguiding over projected achievements and therefore it needs to be cured on priority. The issues raised involve direct and continuing Pan India violation of Fundamental Rights under Articles 14, 21, 21-A statutory rights under the RTE Act, 2009, the RPwD Act, 2016 and centrally sponsored schemes on school education, requiring uniform constitutional interpretation.

II. Whether the present state of school education in States & Union Territories violates international obligation, articles 14, 21 and 21-A of Indian Constitution and the Right of children to free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act, 2009

Despite constitutional guarantees and enactment of the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009, the school education system across Indian States is afflicted by systemic failures, including:[20]

- Severe shortage of trained teachers
- High pupil-teacher ratios in general
- Mismanagement in posting of teachers/ Unreasonable deployment of teachers in the schools where there are no students

- Poor school infrastructure and sanitation
- Learning poverty and poor foundational literacy
- Digital divide and inequitable access
- Regional and inter-State disparities
- Weak implementation of NEP-2020 & RTE Act, 2009
- Exclusion of pre-primary education from enforceable rights
- Underutilisation of funds by the concerned Department & schools.

Foundational Education Gap: Government Schools versus Privately Managed Schools

The deep social & economic disparity exposed by the “Comprehensive Modular Survey: Education” (NSS 80th Round)” & UDISE+ are serious markers of perpetuating inequality. As per the Survey Report, 66% students in rural India and 30.1% students in urban areas are directly dependent on govt. schools for their education.[21] A household is required to make the first school choice of their children primarily based on their average annual income. Discrimination in education starts at the beginning and lays an inequitable path for the entire life of the child who are educated in such government schools which lacks in basic infrastructure and quality education. Surveys signal that the idea of equity in education at government sponsored schools is sabotaged at the very foundational level of pre-primary & primary grades. Students from economically weaker class are systemically accustomed to educational “goods and services” of the schools that fit their household income standards and accept the differences between theirs and their counterparts passed out from privately owned schools as natural and normal.[22] This impacts such young minds & normalises any unfair treatments in their future as natural and non-political. There are deep-rooted disparities driven by type of schools, geography and household income in Indian Society.[23]

Key Findings:

- Dominance of private school in urban areas v. dependence on government schools in rural India.[24]
- Foundational inequality begins before Class I as provision for free pre-schooling are kept under the discretionary power of the appropriate government.[25]

Constitutional Issue:

Structural inequality at foundational stage undermines **substantive equality**. The failure is not sporadic but systemic, persistent, and nationwide, necessitating constitutional intervention.

Government data and independent studies on the issue consistently reveal that learning outcomes in the government schools are alarmingly low, even where enrolment is high, defeating the purpose of compulsory education. It is surprising to know that in some states approx 40% to 50% students studying in class VIII of rural schools are not able to read the class II level text,[26] which itself exposes the condition of learning outcome in such schools. Structural inequality at foundational stage disproportionately affected the learning outcome, resulting in structural inequality, contrary to the spirit of articles 14 and 15 of the Constitution.

Despite substantial budgetary allocations to school education under Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan, State education budgets, and centrally sponsored schemes, ground-level deficiencies persist in infrastructure, teacher availability, learning materials, accessibility, and CwSN support.

Official reports and audit observations reveal that in several States:

1. Funds remain unutilised or under-utilised at the end of the financial year[27]
2. Releases of funds are delayed due to administrative lapses[28]
3. Expenditure is skewed towards non-priority or non-outcome-linked heads & essential expenditures are frequently overlooked[29]
4. Allocations for critical components such as teacher training,[30] accessibility, transport and escort allowances[31] are diverted or parked, or surrendered.

As a result, schools continue to face artificial resource scarcity, not due to lack of allocation but due to inefficient planning, lack of coordination within administration, lack of transparency, weak financial governance, and absence of accountability. It has been seen that states frequently cite “lack of funds” to justify non-compliance with statutory duties, even where sanctioned funds are available, thereby frustrating constitutional guarantees.

Facts Relating to Children with Special Needs (CwSN)

Approx 21,49,258 children enrolled from foundation grade to secondary grade in Indian schools, are Children with Special Needs (CwSN),[32] which also includes children with locomotor, visual, hearing, intellectual, and multiple disabilities. Government data under UDISE+ and implementation reports under Samagra Shiksha reveal that:[33].

1. There are approx. 21,49,258 CwSN enrolled in different types of schools[34], and huge numbers of eligible CwSN are not receiving escort/transport allowances despite sanction.
2. Disbursement is often delayed, parked or transferred to inactive accounts.
3. Many schools lack wheelchair-friendly ramps, handrails, and accessible toilets.
4. Assistive devices such as wheelchairs, hearing aids, and learning aids are either unavailable or grossly insufficient.
5. In rural and tribal areas, absence of escort support forces parents to withdraw children with disabilities from schools, leading to high dropout rates among CwSN.

These failures negate the very object of inclusive education and result in constructive exclusion of disabled children from mainstream schooling.

Budget allocation

6% of the total GDP of the state to be allocated for education purpose but actual data is much below standard set under NEP (2020), the recommendation of Kothari Commission[35] & the United Nation.

It is a long-standing policy goal that India should allocate 6% of its GDP to education, a target that has been consistently reiterated but never met. The actual spending has remained significantly lower, hovering around 3-4% of GDP in recent years.

The 6% Target in fund allocation for education:

- Origin: The goal was first recommended by the Kothari Commission in 1964-66, which suggested increasing education spending to 6% of GNP (Gross National Product) by 1985-86.
- Reiteration: This target was reaffirmed in the National Policy on Education (NPE) in 1986 and again in the more recent National Education Policy (NEP) 2020.
- RTE Act, 2009: While the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act, 2009, established education as a fundamental right for children aged 6 to 14, it did not explicitly mandate the 6% figure within the Act's text, but its effective implementation was estimated to require resources near this level. The funding for the Act is shared between the Central and State Governments (in a 65:35 ratio generally), but the overall budgetary allocations have remained inadequate.

Current Reality

The actual total expenditure on education by both central and state governments combined has consistently fallen short of the 6% benchmark.[36]

- For the year 2022, the total education expenditure as a percentage of GDP was approximately 4.1%.[37] It was 3.9% in year 2019, 4.3% in year 2020 & 4.6% in year 2021.[38]
- There are significant disparities among states, with some spending a higher proportion of their GSDP on education (e.g., Jammu and Kashmir at 8.11% in a specific year) while others spend much less (e.g., Delhi at 1.67%).[39]

This persistent underfunding presents major challenges for the education system, impacting infrastructure, teacher shortages and training gaps, and access to digital learning tools, which ultimately affects the quality of education delivered.

Deficiency in Planning:

It has been observed that approx. 20,817 teachers are deployed in 7,993 schools having zero student enrolment and 1,04,125 schools are run by single teacher who are accommodating 33,76,769 students in the country.[40] Paragraphs 14.3, 14.4 and 14.5 of the Samagra Shiksha Implementation Framework (SSIF) envisage planning as a continuous process that helps to reach a particular goal or objective in the shortest and the best possible way.[41] This process of planning includes long-term perspective plans and annual plans for universalisation of education within the stipulated time frame. The planning process should be bottom-up, participatory, beginning with the Performance Audit Report on School Education in the State, formation of a core planning team at different levels and development of plans after assessing the local specificity, educational needs & aspirations of the people, based on consultative meetings and interaction with the community and target groups.

As stated in the Performance Audit Report 2018-23 on School Education in the State of Odisha conducted by CAG, following findings alongwith conclusions are outlined below: [42]

1. The School and Mass Education Department had not prepared the Perspective Plan for the period 2018-20. The Perspective Plans for the years 2020-21 onwards had primarily used the Unified District Information System for Education (UDISE)+ data sources relating to schools, student's enrolment, infrastructure and teachers, instead of following a bottom-up approach i.e., through household surveys.

2. School Management Committees (SMCs)/ School Management and Development Committees (SMDCs) had not been constituted in seven out of 85 sampled Government and Government-aided schools during 2018-23. Thirty-eight schools had not prepared School Development Plans, despite constitution of SMCs and SMDCs. Apart from this, district level planning team had not been constituted in any of the sampled districts and none of the sampled blocks had constituted the block level planning team, as of March 2023. Thus, the process of planning was not bottom-up despite being envisaged in the SSIF.
3. Spending by the State on education ranged between 3.50% (2018-19) and 3.27% (2022-23) of the GSDP for 2018-23, against the recommendation made in the National Education Policy (1968) to spend at least 6 per cent of GSDP. The Department surrendered ₹ 1,159.31 crore in FY 2019-22, from the budgetary allocation made for the capital expenditure. This is indicative of inability of the Department to create tangible educational assets, despite existence of damaged infrastructure in large number of schools in the sampled districts.
4. CAG Report also objected on to use of UDISE+ data for preparation of the State Perspective Plan as it is not acceptable since the data of only existing schools was captured in UDISE+ which helped in identifying deficiencies in existing schools, but the assessment for educational needs and aspirations of the local population was not captured in that.
5. Absence of participatory and bottom-up planning SSIF stipulates participatory and bottom-up planning to reflect the local specificity, educational needs and aspirations of the people. Report Statistics shows that the educational needs and concerns of the local stakeholders were not taken into consideration in formulation of the district and State plans.
6. Non-preparation of School Safety Plan In pursuance of the direction of the Hon'ble Supreme Court of India, SME Department issued (February 2018) Plan of Action to all DEOs for preparation of the School Disaster Management Plan (SDMP) and School Safety Plan (SSP) for ensuring security and safety of children in all categories of Elementary and Secondary schools. As per the modalities, the SMCs/ SMDCs in Government and Government-aided schools and the management of the Private unaided schools shall prepare the SSPs. The State Advisory Council (December 2015) constituted under the RTE Act, advised the Government to ensure fire safety measures in all schools. But as per the Audit Report, it is concluded that the state and the district authorities had failed to ensure preparation and implementation of school safety plans and measures for the safety of the students.

School Infrastructure:

As per of the report for year 2024-25 published by the Ministry of Education, condition of infrastructure in the country is as under:[43].

1. 7,665 government Schools & government aided schools in the country are lacking drinking water facility.[44].
2. CwSN functional toilet facility is available only in 32.1% government schools.[45].
3. Ramp & handrails are not available in 36.9% of government schools & 42.6% of government aided schools.[46].
4. Computer facility is in not available in 39.8% government schools.[47].
5. Internet facility is not available in 41.2% of government schools.[48].
6. 72.6% of government Schools and 60% of government aided schools in the country are not having the functional facility & infrastructure for rainwater harvesting.[49].
7. Playgrounds are not available in 17% of schools.[50].
8. The Report discloses nonavailability of girl's toilet and functional girl's toilet in 64,126 government schools in the entire nation.[51].
9. The report discloses that approx. 37,493 government schools and numbers of government aided schools are lacking hand wash facility.[52].

The Report also highlights low "Gross Enrolment Ratio" in foundation classes, i.e. 41.4%. [53].

UDISE+ Report of year 2024-25 shows that the dropout rate in primary classes is 11.4% & 9.3% for middle classes in Bihar; Meghalaya and Mizoram are also having higher dropout rate at primary and middle level which is much higher than the National Dropout Rate.[54]. These statistics are quite alarming and demands proper implementation of Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan & RTE Act, 2009.

Infrastructure for ICT Lab, Computer facility, Internet connectivity or online resources & Implementation of Digital initiative in Government schools & Government aided schools

4.4 million government school teachers don't have access to connectivity or computers and 120 million students from government schools don't have access to connectivity of computers.[55]. Only 24% of Government Schools and 60.4% of Government Aided Schools having functional Desktop/ PC available with them.[56]. Only 11.2% of Government Schools and 30.2% of Government Aided Schools are having functional Laptop/Notebook available with them.[57]. Only 5.7% of Government Schools and 16.6%

of Government Aided Schools are having PCs with functional Integrated Teaching Learning Devices available.[58]. Only 16.1% of Government Schools and 44.4% of Government Aided Schools in the country are having functional Projector available.[59]. However, only 3.9% of government schools in Bihar and with 3.2% of government schools at Madhya Pradesh are having projector enabled classroom facility which is far below the national average.[60]. Only 28.6% of Government Schools and 36.5% of Government Aided Schools are having functional Smart Classrooms used for teaching with Digital Boards/ Smart Boards/ Virtual Classrooms/ Smart TV available. Meghalaya is having 1.4%, West Bengal have 5.7%, Bihar is having 11.4% of government schools having digital boards/ virtual classrooms.[61]. The percentage of schools having functional smart classroom, in these states are much below the national average. Only 5.4% of Government Schools and 11% of Government Aided Schools are having facility of Digital Library.[62]. Only 21.2% of Government Schools and Government Aided Schools with Middle & Secondary sections having ICT and Functional ICT Labs.[63].

III. Legal grounds for judicial review of education system at government schools & government aided schools under the RTE Act, 2009

Violation of international obligations

India has ratified the United Nation Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) in year 1992[64]. United Nation Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) on 01/10/2007[65]. & adopted Sustainable Development Goal-4 (SDG-4) in year 2015[66]. making it obligatory on the state to ensure inclusive, accessible, supportive and quality school education for the child.

Relevant provisions of UNCRC pertaining to education rights of the child

Article 23 of UNCRC talks about the rights of disabled child and confers duty on the state to recognise & ensure that a mentally or physically disabled child should enjoy full decent life with dignity & active participation in the community.[67]. It also cast duty on the States Parties to recognize the right of the disabled child to special care, encouragement and ensure the extension of assistance to the eligible child and those responsible for his or her care subject to available resources.[68]. It also binds the state parties to provide for free assistance to such disabled child, effective access to receive education & in a manner favourable to the child's achieving the fullest possible social integration and development.[69]. Article 28(1) obligates the state parties to make primary education compulsory and available free for every child. It also cast duty on the state parties to make educational and vocational information and guidance available and accessible to all children and take measures to encourage regular attendance at schools and the reduction of drop-out rates.[70].

United Nation Convention on the rights of person with disability:

Accessibility: States Parties shall take appropriate measures to ensure the proper accessibility of physical environment, transportation, and other facilities provided to the public and to identify & eliminate obstacles and accessibility barriers of all facilities in the school.[71]. It also binds state parties to provide signage in Braille and in easy to read and understand forms in the schools, its offices, classrooms, toilets, any other buildings open for public use and mandates them to provide forms of live assistance and intermediaries, including guides, readers and professional sign language interpreters, to facilitate accessibility to buildings and other facilities open to the public.[72].

According to article 21 of the convention State Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that persons with disabilities can exercise the right to freedom of expression and opinion, including the freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas on an equal basis with others and through all forms of communication of their choice, as defined in article 2 of the present Convention by Providing information intended for the general public to persons with disabilities in accessible formats and technologies appropriate to different kinds of disabilities in a timely manner and without additional cost and facilitating the use of sign languages, Braille, augmentative and alternative communication, and all other accessible means, modes and formats of communication of their choice by persons with disabilities in official interactions.[73].

Under the provision of article 24 of the convention, States Parties who have ratified it shall ensure the following:[74].

(a) Persons with disabilities are not excluded from the general education system because of their disability, and that children with disabilities are not excluded from free and compulsory primary education, or from secondary education, based on their disability.

(b) Persons with disabilities can access an inclusive, quality and free primary education and secondary education on an equal basis with others in the communities in which they live.

(c) Convention mandates the State Parties to Facilitate the learning of Braille, alternative script, augmentative and alternative modes, means and formats of communication and orientation and mobility skills, Facilitating the learning of sign language and the

promotion of the linguistic identity of the deaf community by employing teachers, including teachers with disabilities, who are qualified in sign language and/or Braille, and to train professionals and staff who work at all levels of education.

SDG-4:

There are ten targets of SDG-4, among these two are mandated to achieve free quality education with universal coverage. First target is to obtain universal coverage for all girls & boys & to achieve free quality education at primary & secondary level of schooling with relevant and effective learning outcomes by year 2030.

Second target is to ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education.

India has formally adopted the SDG-4 goal in year 2015 which obligates the central government, state governments and union territories to make such policies for its effective implementation in such a way that it can achieve the goal within given timeline.

Statistics illustrated in Part II of this research paper shows that there is great mismatch between ground level implementation and the ratified convention even after years of government initiatives & centre funded schemes.

Violation of article 14 & article 21-A of the Constitution:

States have failed to provide meaningful, quality education, rendering Article 21-A illusory.[75] India has 10,92,671 Government Schools/ Government aided Schools[76], with 59,07,395 teachers[77] and 14,63,51,437 students up to Secondary level[78]. Official data reveals following outcome:

(i) Adverse Pupil-Teacher Ratio (PTR) persists at upper-primary, secondary, and higher secondary levels in multiple States.

(ii) Large inter-State variation in:

- Functional toilets (especially girls' toilets)
- Electricity and internet connectivity
- Availability of trained teachers

(iii) Significant number of schools lack:

- Functional libraries
- Digital infrastructure
- CWSN-friendly access (ramps, toilets)

Disparities in basic schooling facilities violate Article 14 (equality) and render Article 21-A ineffective. Unequal quality of schooling in government administered or government financed schools across States and socio-economic groups results in hostile discrimination.

Violation of article 21: Education is inseparable from dignity, livelihood, and informed citizenship hence any type of deprivation or access denial due to lack of infrastructure or other authorised resources will amount to violation of article 21 of the Constitution. "Court has already elaborated the scope of right guaranteed under article 21 while interpreting it in the light of article 41 and article 45 of the constitution. In *Unnikrishnan v. State of Andhra Pradesh* honourable court held that every child /citizen of this country has a right to free education until he completes the age of Fourteen years. Thereafter his Right to Education is subject to the limits of economic capacity and development of the state.[79]

Failure to implement statutory duties

1. Non-compliance with the RTE Act, poor planning & financial management, lack of habitation wise school mapping, noncompliance of statutory obligations by states for children with special needs & girl students, infrastructure standards, teacher norms, students' entitlements and grievance redressal mechanisms.[80]
2. As per the year 2025 report published by the World Bank in South Asia, despite figures indicating very positive increases in enrolment rates and gender parity among students (as indicated by the UN statistics), academic outcomes are still poor throughout the region (Asim et al. 2015). It says that a major reason for this is the short length of the school day in some countries in the region such as India where the school day typically lasts for only three hours compared to six to eight hours per day on average in OECD countries (Banerjee and Duflo 2011). In addition, there is evidence that starting the school day later, for adolescents especially, can be beneficial as it fits with their natural cycle of alertness during the day (Lockley 2015).[81]
3. World Bank Report also reveals that health of Teachers and students both are affected by the hygiene condition of the school, hence affecting their overall academic performance. It illustrates that Teachers are not immune to health and safety concerns. Researchers from several lending institutions and universities made unannounced visits to primary schools in Bangladesh, Ecuador, India,

Indonesia, Peru, and Uganda in 2006 and found that about 19 percent of teachers were absent. To try to understand this phenomenon, they constructed an index measuring the quality of the school's infrastructure that included whether the school had a toilet, covered classrooms, non-dirt floors, electricity, or a school library. The analysis for the sample as a whole suggested that: "moving from a school with the lowest infrastructure index score to one with the highest (that is, from a score of zero to five) is associated with a 10-percentage point reduction in teacher absence." This conclusion echoed the results of studies in 2004 and 2016 that found a strong relationship between teachers' perceptions of the maintenance and condition of the buildings and their intentions to stay or leave the profession. The state of the infrastructure was found to be a more significant factor than their salary levels.[82].

Violation of article 21-A read with article 15(3) & 15(4) of the Constitution:

The right to free and compulsory education under Article 21-A necessarily includes reasonable accommodation and additional support for children with disabilities. Denial of such support amounts to indirect discrimination. Exclusion of children with disabilities through infrastructural neglect and administrative apathy is a form of Constitutional Violence, impermissible in a right based democracy.

Non-compliance with the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016

Sections 16, 17, and 31 of the RPWD Act mandate:[83].

1. Inclusive education
2. Barrier-free access
3. Reasonable accommodation
4. Support services including transport and escort

Persistent non-compliance of section 16, 17 & 31 renders the state actions illegal, arbitrary, and unconstitutional.

Failure of statutory obligations under the RTE Act, 2009

The RTE Act read with Rules and Samagra Shiksha guidelines requires:

1. Neighbourhood access to schools[84]
2. Special training and support for disadvantaged groups[85].
3. Removal of physical and social barriers[86].
4. Maintaining record of all children in its jurisdiction through household survey from their birth till they attain 14 years of age.[87]

(UDISE+ Report 2024-25, Teacher Deployment & Training)

Key Findings:[88]

1. Thousands of schools operate with single teachers with multi-grade classrooms.
2. Shortfall of professionally trained teachers in government schools.
3. Teacher rationalisation policies remain poorly implemented.

Legal relevance:

Failure to appoint adequate teachers[89] defeats statutory obligations under Section 23 & 25 of the RTE Act, 2009.

1. Latest official data under UDISE+ reveals that while some schools and districts operate with surplus teachers, a large number of government schools—particularly in rural, tribal, and urban-poor areas—suffer from acute teacher shortages, resulting in high and unevenly distributed pupil-teacher ratios (PTR).
2. Several schools operate with single-teacher or two-teacher models across multiple grades, forcing multi-grade teaching and significantly impairing learning outcomes.
3. The problem is not absence of sanctioned posts but ineffective teacher deployment and rationalisation, leading to structural inequity among similarly placed students.
4. Children from disadvantaged groups, including Children with Special Needs (CwSN), are disproportionately affected, as high PTR makes individualized attention and reasonable accommodation impossible.

Uneven and Excessive Pupil-Teacher Ratio[90] Violates Articles 14, 21 & 21-A

- (i) The right to education under Article 21-A necessarily includes access to adequate and reasonably distributed teaching personnel.
- (ii) Unequal PTR across schools and districts, without rational justification, results in hostile discrimination between similarly situated children, violating Article 14.
- (iii) Excessive PTR directly undermines:

- Quality of instruction
- Classroom engagement
- Individual attention
- Learning outcomes

(iv) Schools with severe teacher shortages effectively provide illusory education, violating the right to life with dignity under Article 21.

Hence, State is required to ensure compliance with PTR norms under Section 25 & Schedule (for Norms & Standard prescribed for schools) of the RTE Act in every school, within a time-bound schedule and conduct annual teacher rationalisation exercises, using CAG Reports on Performance Audit of Schools, UDISE+ data, ASER 2024 Report & World Bank reports, to ensure equitable distribution. A school deficient in learning resources or worn-out classroom buildings or with grossly inadequate teachers or highly adverse PTR, is a school only in name; constitutionally, it is a denial of right to quality education.

Statutory Violation of RTE Act, 2009

1. The Act confers right to every child between the age of six to fourteen years, shall have the right to free and compulsory education in a neighbourhood school till the completion of his or her elementary education.[91] Provision of section 3, 8 & 9 of the Act cast well defined duties on the state & Local Authorities to provide for the means to achieve the goal of facilitating elementary schooling to each & every child falling between the prescribed age group which also includes the child from weaker section and the disadvantaged group.[92] The scheme of the section is to bind the state to provide infrastructure which also includes school building, teaching staff & there training facility, learning equipment and to ensure good quality elementary education conforming to the standards and norms specified in the Schedule of the Act.[93]
2. Section 25 of the RTE Act, 2009 mandates that the appropriate Government shall ensure that pupil–teacher ratio is maintained in each school.
3. Persistent operation of schools with single teachers or grossly excessive PTR constitutes a continuing breach of statutory duty.
4. Failure to rationalise teacher deployment, despite available data and authority, is arbitrary and unreasonable.
5. Administrative Inertia and Non-Implementation of Policy as despite availability of real-time data through UDISE+, States have failed to:
 - Undertake scientific teacher rationalisation
 - Ensure equitable distribution
 - Periodically review PTR compliance
6. Such inaction amounts to arbitrariness, offending Article 14.

Judicially Enforceable Obligation

1. Hon'ble Supreme Court has held that where statutory norms exist, courts can enforce them through mandamus [94] and continuing mandamus.[95]

Supporting Judicial Precedents are as under:

In *Devesh Sharma v. Union of India & Ors.*, hon'ble Supreme Court stressed that "right to education not only includes free and compulsory but also encompass meaningful and quality education".[96] The court held that teachers must possess the appropriate pedagogical skills and specialized training for the specific educational level they teach. In *Society for Unaided Private Schools of Rajasthan v. Union of India*, Court held that norms set under the Right to Free & Compulsory Education Act, 2009 are mandatory in nature with some exceptions pertaining to unaided minority & non-minority schools not receiving any kind of aid or grant to meet their expenses from the appropriate governments or local authorities.[97]

Arbitrary and discriminatory disbursement of escort allowances to Children with Special Needs (CsWN)

- (i) Non-disbursement, delayed disbursement, or incorrect transfer of escort allowances: -
 - (a) Defeats the purpose of welfare schemes
 - (b) Imposes disproportionate financial burden on poor families
 - (c) Leads to unequal access to education
- (ii) Financial mismanagement cannot justify non-compliance with RPWD Act:
 - (a) Escort allowances, assistive devices, accessibility infrastructure, and support services for CwSN are statutory entitlements, not optional expenditures.
 - (b) As held in *Vikash Kumar v. UPSC & Ors.*,[98] reasonable accommodation for disabled person by the state cannot be denied on grounds of administrative or financial inconvenience.

Such arbitrariness in disbursement of escort allowances and non-compliance of provisions of the RPWD Act, 2016 violates Article 14.

Precise alignment with the RPwD ACT, 2016 & Rules

Statutory framework

(i) Duty of Educational Institutions: The appropriate Government and the local authorities shall endeavour that all educational institutions funded or recognised by them provide inclusive education to the children with disabilities and towards that end shall[99]

—

- (a) admit them without discrimination and provide education and opportunities for sports and recreation activities equally with others.
- (b) make building, campus and various facilities accessible.
- (c) provide reasonable accommodation according to the individual's requirements.
- (d) provide necessary support individualised or otherwise in environments that maximise academic and social development consistent with the goal of full inclusion.
- (e) ensure that the education to persons who are blind or deaf or both is imparted in the most appropriate languages and modes and means of communication.
- (f) detect specific learning disabilities in children at the earliest and take suitable pedagogical and other measures to overcome them.
- (g) monitor participation, progress in terms of attainment levels and completion of education in respect of every student with disability.
- (h) provide transportation facilities to the children with disabilities and also the attendant of the children with disabilities having high support needs.

Violation pleaded:

Failure to provide escorts allowance, transportation allowance, accessible school infrastructure, and assistive devices for learning to the disabled students renders the "appropriate environment" illusory. Non-availability of ramps, handrails, accessible toilets, escorts, and delayed allowance disbursement is a direct breach of section 16 of the Act.

(ii) Specific Measures for Inclusive Education

Mandates the State to:

- (a) to train and employ teachers, including teachers with disability who are qualified in sign language and Braille and teachers who are trained in teaching children with intellectual disability;[100]
- (b) to train professionals and staff to support inclusive education at all levels of school education;[101]
- (c) to promote the use of appropriate augmentative and alternative modes including means and formats of communication, Braille and sign language to supplement the use of one's own speech to fulfil the daily communication needs of persons with speech, communication or language disabilities and enables them to participate and contribute to their community and society;[102]
- (d) to provide books, other learning materials and appropriate assistive devices to students with benchmark disabilities free of cost up to the age of eighteen years; [103]
- (e) to provide scholarships in appropriate cases to students with benchmark disability;[104]
- (f) to make suitable modifications in the curriculum and examination system to meet the needs of students with disabilities such as extra time for completion of examination paper, facility of scribe or amanuensis, exemption from second and third language courses;[105]
- (g) to promote research to improve learning;[106] and
- (h) any other measures, as may be required.[107]

Violation pleaded

(a) Teachers trained in use of sign language, Braille script and teaching method for intellectually disabled students, professionals and trained staff to support them are found deficient in schools.

(b) Training centres to promote the use of appropriate augmentative and alternative modes including means and formats of communication, Braille and sign language

required at each District Headquarter.

(c) Data pertaining to grant of Scholarships & support allowances in appropriate cases to students with benchmark disability is not available in public domain.

(iii) Free Education for Children with Benchmark Disabilities

The appropriate Government and local authorities shall ensure that every child with benchmark disability between the age of six to eighteen years shall have the right to free education in an appropriate environment at a neighbourhood school, or in a special school, of his choice.[108].

Violation pleaded:

Absence of transport/escort support makes "neighbourhood school" inaccessible and lack of specially trained teachers & staff for them makes it meaningless.

Accessibility Standards

Empowers the Central Government to notify mandatory accessibility standards for persons with disabilities laying down the standards of accessibility for physical environment, transportation, information and communications, including appropriate technologies and systems, and other facilities and services provided to the public in urban and rural areas.[109]

Legal consequence:

Mandatory accessibility standards once notified, its compliance become non-discretionary.

Punitive Consequences

Non-compliance with statutory duties under the RPWD Act, 2016 attracts penalties.[110]

Harmonious reading with the RTE act, 2009

Children with disabilities are entitled to free and compulsory education[111]. "subject to the provisions of the RPWD Act".

Supreme Court precedents on disability rights:

1. In *Rajneesh Kumar Pandey & ors. v. Union of India*, hon'ble Supreme Court has laid down the guidelines regarding maintaining specific Pupil -Teacher's ratio for different types of disabled students and also upheld the requirement of compulsory training to the special teacher as well as to the general teacher keeping in mind the requirement of CsWN.[112].

2. *Jeeja Ghosh v. Union of India*[113].

Key Principles:

It was pronounced that equality is founded upon two complementary principles in international human right law, i.e (i) Non-discrimination (ii) Reasonable differentiation. The subject of the rights of persons with disabilities should be approached from human rights perspective, which recognise that person with disabilities were entitled to enjoy full range of internationally guaranteed rights and freedom without discrimination on the ground of disability. It was also upheld that denial of reasonable accommodation to the disabled person violates article 21 & right to be treated with human & dignity is the core of disability jurisprudence.

3. *Vikash Kumar v. Union Public Service Commission & Ors.*[114].

Key Holdings:

Reasonable accommodation is a constitutional requirement, not discretionary power and its determinations must be made on a case-by-case basis, in consultation with the disabled person concerned. Equality for persons with disabilities means substantive equality, not formal equality and administrative convenience of the state are no defence which is directly applicable to escorts allowance, transport facilities, infrastructure, allowances & assistive devices for persons with benchmark disability as in addition to its observation described in the last sentence, hon'ble Supreme Court also upheld that while framing the guidelines regarding access to required reasonable accommodation by the candidate appearing in U.P.S.C exam, state must ensure that persons with disability are not required to bear the cost of the reasonable accommodation.

4. *Rajive Raturi v. Union of India* [115].

In this landmark case pertaining to accessibility right of the disabled person, Court viewed it as integral part of right to life and directed the Central & State government to ensure barrier free access, specifically citing section 44 & 45 of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016. The judgment emphasized the social model of disability requiring the removal of physical and systemic barriers in public infrastructures and transport. It Mandates that all government buildings & transport services be made accessible for people with blindness by taking various measures like providing Braille Signboards and other such facilities at such places. Court also laid down the broad guideline to safeguard the accessibility right of the person suffering from disability and recommended for continuous consultation and improvement of accessibility infrastructure at public places & public transport system.

5. *Disabled Rights Group v. Union of India*[116].

In this case court held that denying proper educational facilities to differently abled individuals amount to discrimination and instructed the state to make infrastructure & pedagogy adequate and conducive to the requirement of such individuals.

All these landmark judgments by the hon'ble Supreme Court have given a new direction to the disability jurisprudence and proved complementary to the state policies by its rich perspective on disability rights.

K. DOCTRINE OF SUBSTANTIVE EQUALITY

Formal equality (concept of Identical treatment) is inadequate for children with disabilities. The Constitution needs substantive equality means true equality which requires recognizing and addressing different needs & binds the State to obligate additional support, not identical treatment.

L. 1. (ASER 2022 / 2023/2024 : Learning Outcomes Crisis)

Source: Annual Status of Education Report (ASER)

Key Findings:[117].

1. Major percentage of students in Class V cannot read Class II text. More or less it's similar to other higher grades too.
2. Basic arithmetic skills remain poor even at upper-primary level.
3. Learning loss post-pandemic remains unaddressed in many States.

Judicial Significance:

Right to education is not mere enrolment but includes meaningful learning.[118].

2. (NAS 2021 Report – NCERT: National Achievement Survey)

Source: NCERT, Ministry of Education

Key Findings:[119].

- Learning outcomes in Mathematics, Science, and Language remain below benchmark.
- Stark rural–urban and government–private gaps.
- Teacher training quality directly correlates with student performance.

Legal Relevance:

State failure to improve outcomes violates positive obligations under Article 21.

Violation of article 14 & 21 due to mismanagement and inefficient utilisation or under-utilisation of education funds[120], as it primarily oversteps upon economic, social & cultural rights. It also obstructs the state's ability to deliver basic services & violates the principle of equitable resources distribution.

1. Persistent lack of resources at school level is not due to absence of allocation, but due to inefficient planning, delayed releases, diversion, and under-utilisation of funds.
2. Mismanagement of funds earmarked for education constitutes constructive denial of fundamental rights.
3. The State cannot plead financial constraints where allocated funds are misused or remain unutilised (*Ratlam Municipality; Paschim Banga*).
4. The plea of financial constraint is unavailable where allocated public funds are mismanaged, under-utilised, or inequitably deployed.
5. The right to education under Articles 21 and 21-A includes a positive obligation on the State to plan, allocate, and utilise resources effectively to realise the right.
6. Administrative mismanagement resulting in resource deprivation amounts to constructive denial of fundamental rights.
7. Violation of Article 14 Through Arbitrary Financial Governance

- Uneven and opaque fund utilisation across districts and schools, without rational basis, results in hostile discrimination between similarly situated students.
- Schools suffering due to administrative lapses are placed at a disadvantage for reasons unrelated to merit, need, or policy, violating Article 14.

Breach of Fiduciary Duty and Public Trust Doctrine

Education funds are held by the State in trust for children. Mismanagement, diversion, or non-utilisation violates fiduciary responsibility and attracts constitutional scrutiny.

Failure to Implement NEP-2020 and Samagra Shiksha in Letter and Spirit

Despite policy commitments, lack of outcome-linked implementation and accountability has resulted in policy paralysis, defeating constitutional goals.

(i) Statutory Breach of Samagra Shiksha and RTE Framework

1. The Samagra Shiksha scheme mandates annual planning, Outcome-based budgeting and timely release and utilisation of funds.
2. Failure to adhere to these conditions constitutes a breach of statutory and contractual obligations binding upon the States.
3. Section 7 of the RTE Act, 2009 casts a joint responsibility on the Union and States to provide financial resources for implementation.

Public Trust Doctrine and Fiduciary Obligation

1. Public funds allocated for education are held by the State in trust for children.
2. Mismanagement, diversion, or non-utilisation of such funds constitutes a breach of fiduciary duty and attracts constitutional scrutiny.

Supporting judicial precedents

1. ***Municipal Council, Ratlam v. Vardhichand***[\[121\]](#) In this case Court held that it could compel a statutory body to carry out its public duty to the community on a time-bound basis by affirmative action and it also observed that the statutory bodies can't be validly exonerated from their statutory liability on the basis of its financial inability.
2. ***Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Samity v. State of West Bengal***[\[122\]](#) 16. *In the context of the constitutional obligation to provide free legal aid to a poor accused this Court has held that the State cannot avoid its constitutional obligation in that regard on account of financial constraints. The said observations would apply with equal, if not greater, force in the matter of discharge of constitutional obligation of the State has to be kept in view.*"
3. In ***Centre for Public Interest Litigation v. Union of India***[\[123\]](#), hon'ble Supreme Court held that public property/ natural resources of the State must be managed transparently and in public interest.

Conclusion

After deliberate analysis of above illustrated facts & data mentioned under Part-II of the paper, it is concluded that in spite of the proactive approach and initiatives of the government, official data reveals persistent deficiencies in the education of government schools & government aided schools.[\[124\]](#) Accuracy of data pertaining to performance indicators also came under question in the Report regarding Performance Audit of government schools of Odisha for year 2018-2023 prepared by CAG. Digitalisation of all such schools and mandatory online disclosure of data pertaining to Pupil Teacher Ratio, infrastructure, accessibility & support allowances for CwSN, learning outcome, dropout rates, budgeting & expenses may facilitate better transparency and accountability in school administration.

It is also evident that India has ratified the UNCRC & signed the SDG-4, hence it cast the duty on the state to ensure the educational rights of the child in terms of as prescribed under the convention & also as per the provision of domestic law on school education. It obligates the state parties to make primary education compulsory and available free for every child & cast duty on them to make educational and vocational information and guidance available and accessible to all children and take measures to encourage regular attendance at schools and the reduction of drop-out rates.[\[125\]](#)

Unequal quality of schooling in government administered or government financed schools across States and socio-economic groups results in hostile discrimination & against the spirit of article 14 of Indian Constitution. Exclusion of children with disabilities through infrastructural neglect and administrative apathy is a form of constitutional violence, impermissible in a rights-based democracy. It is also observed that the state's failure to provide basic access infrastructure, escort support, and care services violates article 21, the right to live with dignity, autonomy, mobility, and meaningful participation in education. In ***Devesh Sharma v. Union of India & Ors.***, hon'ble Supreme Court stressed that "right to education" not only includes free and compulsory but also encompass meaningful and quality education.[\[126\]](#)

The *Unnikrishnan v. State of Andhra Pradesh*,^[127] Court upheld the right to free education of every child/ citizen of this country till they complete the age of 14 years and thereafter the right to free education is subject to the limits of economic capacity & development of the state.

Non-compliance with the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016 in considerable numbers of the government schools and government aided schools, is also evident which is infringement to article 21-A of the Constitution too which provides the ground for judicial review.

In *Centre for Public Interest Litigation v. Union of India*^[128], hon'ble Supreme Court held that public property/ natural resources of the State must be managed transparently and in public interest and hence in utilizing the central fund or grant allotted under the schemes run by the government need to be utilized with full transparency & accountability or else may provide ground for judicial review.

As we have seen in *Unnikrishnan case*^[129] where right to education was declared as part of enforceable constitutional right and *Devesh Sharma Case*,^[130] hon'ble Supreme Court has interpreted the right to education in much broader perspective which includes meaningful and quality education. Based on precedence and above illustrated grounds, it is recommended that provision of adequately trained teachers, reasonable pupil-teacher ratio, accessible infrastructure & support services for children with disabilities, uniform minimum standard of school education across all states & UTs, effective utilization of education fund and integration of pre-primary education must be declared as enforceable constitutional rights under the provision of article 21A. Statutory entitlement, its timely disbursement & wheelchair friendly access points for disabled child, are enforceable components of the right to education for children with disabilities, and not discretionary welfare measures.

In addition to this, following measures are recommended for ensuring proper implementation of the government run schemes for improving school education:

(i) State government may constitute an Independent National School Education Monitoring Authority or Court-monitored National Oversight Committee on School Education Reform, comprising education experts, disability rights specialists, representatives of NCERT & NCPER, jurists and outstanding academicians.

(ii) States to ensure effective implementation of NEP-2020 with measurable benchmarks.

(iii) Time-bound compliance with RTE norms (not exceeding 24 months).

(iv) Public disclosure of school-wise PTR, infrastructure status, accessibility, school wise budget allocation and fund utilisation on official portals under the provision of mandatory disclosure under section 4 of the RTI Act, 2005.

(v) Annual public disclosure of school-wise learning outcomes.

(vi) State to frame and implement a time-bound National School Education Reform Action Plan, covering:

- Teacher recruitment and training
- Infrastructure and sanitation
- Foundational literacy and numeracy
- Digital inclusion

(vii) Independent audit of utilisation of school education funds, particularly under Samagra Shiksha and CWSN components.

(viii) Fixing of administrative accountability for diversion, delay, or non-utilisation of education funds.

(ix) Digitalisation of all government schools & government aided schools for fast and accurate collection & analysis of all relevant data and online monitoring by supervising authority.

(x) Given the systemic, nationwide, prolonged and persistent nature of violations, one-time directions are inadequate, hence judicial intervention through continuing mandamus is necessary to secure sustained compliance.

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92. *The Right of the Children to free & Compulsory Education Act, 2009 (Act 35 of 2009), Ss.3,8,9.*
93. *The Right of the Children to free & Compulsory Education Act, 2009 (Act 35 of 2009), The Schedule for Norms and Standards for a School.*
94. *Brij Mohan Lal v. Union of India (2012) 6 SCC 502*
95. *Vineet Narayan v. Union of India (1998) 2 SCC 226*
96. *Civil Appeal No. 5068 OF 2023, the Supreme Court of India 2023 INSC 704*
97. *(2012) 6 SCC 1*
98. *Civil Appeal No. 273 of 2021, Special Leave Petition (C) No. 1882 of 2021*
99. *The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016 (Act 49 Of 2016), s.16.*
100. *Ibid, s. 17(c)*
101. *Ibid, s. 17(d)*
102. *Ibid, s. 17(f)*
103. *Ibid, s. 17(g)*
104. *Ibid, s. 17(h)*
105. *Ibid, s. 17(i)*
106. *Ibid, s. 17(j)*
107. *Ibid, s. 17(k)*
108. *Ibid s. 31.*
109. *Ibid s. 40.*
110. *Ibid s. 89.*
111. *The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009 (Act 35 Of 2009), s. 3(2).*
112. *Rajneesh Kumar Pandey & ors. v. Union of India, Writ Petition (Civil) No. 132 of 2016, Supreme Court of India*
113. *Writ Petition (Civil) 98 of 2012, (2016) 7 SCC 761 at p. no. 43.*
114. *Civil Appeal No. 273 of 2021, Special Leave Petition (C) No. 1882 of 2021.*
115. *(2018) 2 SCC 413, 2024 INSC 858*
116. *(2018) 2 SCC 397*
117. *Supra note 26*
118. *Supra note 96.*
119. *(NAS)-2021 Report Card, Ministry of Education, Department of School Education & Literacy available at <http://www.nas.gov.in/reportcard/2021> last accessed on 27/02/2026*
120. *Supra note 89.*
121. *(1980) 4 SCC 162*
122. *(1996) 4 SCC 37*

123. (2012) 3 SCC 104, MANU/SC/0089/2012
124. *Supra note 89.*
125. *The United Nations Convention on Right of the Child, 1989, Article 28 (1)(b), 28(1)(d) & 28(1)(e).*
126. *Supra note 96*
127. *Supra note 79*
128. *Supra note 123*
129. *Supra note 127*
130. *Supra note 126*